

BOOSTING ONLINE RECALIBRATION OF PHYSICS OBJECTS FOR THE 40 MHZ SCOUTING SYSTEM AT CMS

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Abstract

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This work explores the accelerator capabilities of a modern FPGA board for fast Neural Network inference. The physics application involves the analysis of raw data collected at the Level-1 Global Muon Trigger of CMS detector, with the goal of developing a real-time recalibration of the Level-1 muon primitives to match as closely as possible the parameters of the physics objects of interest. The application is deployed in the 40 MHz Level-1 Trigger Scouting demonstrator of the CMS experiment.

The project is organized in two parts. As a first step, the dataset for training the network, the network architecture and the tools are presented. Depending on the configuration of the hyperparameters, multiple network models are created to optimize the recalibration performances, and tested emulating the hardware implementation. The second and last step focuses on the FPGA resource usage optimization and on the deployment of the network on a Xilinx VCU128 evaluation board. The validation of the implemented optimal design in a test setup is finally discussed.

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1 Introduction

This project is related to the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN, where proton-proton collisions are performed at a previously unprecedented energy and luminosity to probe the internal structure of matter, and the interactions between its constituent particles. In particular, bunches of protons collide at a Bunch Crossing (BX) frequency of 40 MHz, producing an extremely high raw data throughput in the detectors that measure the particles produced in these collisions. It is impossible to fully record all the possible data with current technology. Thus, a first processing and trigger step is required to filter only events with interesting features, based on algorithms implemented on hardware devices like Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs).

Among the possible algorithms, Machine Learning (ML) applications have proven to be very effective for the purpose. In particular, this work involves the implementation of Neural Networks (NNs) on FPGA hardware for the online recalibration of the physics object primitives produced by the Level-1 Trigger processing chain of the Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) experiment at the LHC. The physics primitives taken into account are the candidate muons reconstructed by the muon trigger. The global muon trigger is read-out at the full BX rate by the Level-1 Trigger Scouting system, in which the NN application for Level-1 muon recalibration is hosted.

The content of this work is organized as follows:

- In Section 1, the LHC and CMS experiment are briefly introduced as the topic of this work, with particular emphasis on the Data Acquisition and Trigger parts of CMS and on the Level-1 Trigger Scouting system.
- In Section 2, the Neural Network application is described in all of its development steps, including the physics dataset and software tools used for training.
- The hardware implementation and integration in the Level-1 Trigger Scouting system, namely the main goal of this project, is discussed in Section 3
- A final summary is given in Section 4.

1.1 The Large Hadron Collider

The LHC is the largest and most powerful particle accelerator in the world to date. It is a 27 km ring of two tunnels to accommodate two separate high-energy particle beams. The LHC consists of thousands of superconducting magnets designed to accelerate and bend the beams. It is designed for a 14 TeV center-of-mass collision energy [1]. After the second LHC Long Shutdown (LS2) between 2018-2022, it has now started operating again for LHC Run 3.

The two beams are accelerated in separate vacuum tubes in opposite directions until they reach a speed close to the speed of light c and a target energy. Later, they are injected into colliders as bunches of protons. Bunch crossings in the LHC occur at four different collision points which can be seen in Figure 1:

- CMS, discussed in greater detail in the following Section.
- ATLAS, the other general-purpose detector that investigates a wide range of physics phenomena.
- A Large Ion Collider Experiment (ALICE), a detector dedicated to heavy-ion physics and that studies a phase of matter called quark-gluon plasma, mainly through lead-lead ion collisions.
- The Large Hadron Collider beauty (LHCb), designed to investigate differences between matter and anti-matter by studying beauty (b) quarks.

Figure 1: Schematic view of CERN facilities [2]. The LHC is the last ring (dark blue line) in a complex chain of particle accelerators. The scheme includes also other smaller experiments designed to uncover the fundamental physics of the universe.

1.2 The Compact Muon Solenoid Experiment

The Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) is one of the four main experiments at the LHC, located at Interaction Point 5. It is a general-purpose detector with a varied physics program, which includes Standard Model (SM) physics and Beyond the Standard Model (BSM) searches involving, for example, Dark Matter or extra dimensions [3].

The CMS detector is built around a huge solenoid magnet and it has a multi-layer structure, as shown in the 3D model, Figure 2, and in an octet of its transverse slice, Figure 3. Going from the innermost to the outermost layer, it is composed of:

- **A Silicon Tracker system.** It is made of pixel detectors and silicon micro-strip sensors that are used to track paths of particles emerging from the collisions. It provides high accuracy paths in three-dimensions [6].
- **A Calorimetry system.** It measures the energy of particles with high precision and it is composed of two consecutive subsystems: the Electromagnetic Calorimeter (ECAL) and the Hadron Calorimeter (HCAL). The ECAL subsystem measures photons and electrons by stopping them through lead tungstate crystals. On the other hand, the HCAL measures the energy of hadronic particles that are made of gluons and quarks. They are both composed of a barrel and endcap regions for a more complete coverage [7].
- **A Muon Spectrometer system.** Muons can travel inside the calorimeters without interacting. A complex system, consisting of drift tubes, cathode strip chambers and resistive plate chambers is used to measure their properties [8].

A more detailed description of the CMS detector and its components can be found in [9].

Data Acquisition and Triggering Given the LHC bunch crossing rate and an average event size of $\mathcal{O}(1)$ MB, the CMS detector produces a raw data throughput of $\mathcal{O}(100)$ Tb/s. With the currently available technology, neither storing, nor fully processing data at such a rate is feasible. Therefore, a two-level trigger system is used to filter only specific physics signatures and reduce the overall output to around $\mathcal{O}(01)$ Gb/s [10].

The first level of this trigger system, also known as Level-1 (L1) Trigger, is built with custom FPGA-based processing boards. It selects the interesting events based on a subset of the information coming from the detector and reduces the event rate to around 100 kHz.

Figure 2: 3D Model of the CMS detector [4].

Figure 3: A slice of the CMS detector [5].

Following the L1 Trigger Accept signal (L1A), the full event data is then read-out to the second triggering stage, namely the High Level Trigger (HLT). The HLT consists of a farm of processors running a version of the full event reconstruction software optimized for fast processing, and it reduces the event rate to around 1 kHz before data storage and further analysis [11].

1.3 CMS Level-1 Trigger Scouting Project

Although the two-level trigger system allows a reduction in the event storing rate, due to a limited (100 kHz) rate budget at the Level-1 Trigger stage, only certain physics signatures can be captured. Events with exotic signatures, such as Dark Matter signals and Heavy Stable Charged Particles [12], might be discarded, introducing a bias in the physics searches of the CMS experiment.

The Level-1 Trigger Scouting system is designed to overcome this limitation by collecting and storing the physics primitives and intermediate information of the CMS Level-1 Trigger processing chain, at the full LHC bunch crossing rate. Thus, the Level-1 Scouting system is complementary to the standard CMS DAQ and it allows for a semi-real time analyses, at the cost of having the reduced Level-1 trigger resolution [13].

Run 3 Demonstrator System The Scouting system has been demonstrated in 2018 during LHC Run 2. The demonstrator for Run 3 will gather data from the following sources, as shown in Figure 4, with each link transmitting at 10 Gb/s:

- 8 links from Global Muon Trigger (μ GMT) board;
- 7 links from Calo Layer 2 boards;
- 24 links from 12 Barrel Muon Track Finder (BMTF) boards;
- 18 links from 6 Global Trigger (μ GT) boards.

Figure 4: CMS Level-1 Trigger Scouting system demonstrator for Run 3 [14].

The demonstrator system gathers data with three FPGA-based boards: the Xilinx KCU1500, the Micron SB852 and the Xilinx VCU128. The KCU1500 hosts a KU115 FPGA that is capable of receiving data from up to 8×10 Gb/s optical links. The SB852 includes a Xilinx VU9P FPGA that is compatible with the Micron Deep Learning Accelerator (MDLA). Similarly to the first board, it receives data from up to 8 optical links but at a maximum speed of about 28 Gb/s per link. The VCU128 hosts the VU37P FPGA, which can host up to 40×28 Gb/s optical links with a mezzanine card. After the pre-processing stages on the FPGA, all the boards send data to a host server via PCIe using Direct Memory Access (DMA) [14]. In this project, the case of μ GMT scouting with the VCU128 kit has been considered, focusing on the Level-1 μ GMT muons real-time recalibration using Neural Networks on FPGA hardware.

Firmware A summary and schematic of the firmware used for the scouting of the μ GMT source is shown in Figure 5. The modular structure of the firmware can be divided into pipelined blocks, listed below:

- **Trigger Input receiving logic:** from the μ GMT board, the trigger input comes through 8 optical links at 10 Gb/s. The logic of this module decodes the 8b/10b encoding format coming from the optical links.
- **Comma Gap Cleaner:** padding and special words inside the gap between one LHC orbit and another are invalidated to protect the following logic that detects the start/end of an orbit.
- **Streams Aligner:** it aligns all the streams from each link into a single stream of 8×32 bits per word.
- **BX data Zero Suppression:** if a bunch crossing in an orbit does not have any physical muons, it is suppressed.
- **Buffer FIFO Filler:** includes a state machine to control the filling of buffer FIFOs before the DMA stage. The buffer FIFOs, when enough space is available, are filled with packets made up of a fixed and tunable number of LHC orbits. If they are full, complete LHC orbits are dropped.
- **DMA Engine:** when the host CPU-based computing system is ready to receive data, the orbits in the buffer FIFOs are sent to the DMA core and then sent to the host via 8 PCIe Gen-3 lanes.

Figure 5: L1 μ GMT scouting firmware schematic [14].

2 Online Recalibration in Level-1 Scouting

Collision data coming from CMS detector are complex and the event rate is extremely high. To facilitate and improve the analysis of the collision event at Level-1, Machine Learning techniques can be integrated into the L1 Trigger hardware devices for different purposes, such as BSM anomaly detection, fake muon pair classifiers and recalibration of the μ GMT candidate muons.

The focus of this project is L1 muon primitives recalibration, in the context of the Level-1 Trigger Scouting system. The goal is to achieve the recalibration using a Neural Network integrated on the Xilinx VCU128 evaluation board. This Section introduces more in detail the application and the dataset used to train the Neural Network, the tools used for training and hardware implementation, and the model optimization.

2.1 Dataset for Neural Network training

The main kinematic parameters of L1 muon primitives coming from the μ GMT, are defined taking into account a reference coordinate system for a single collision event as shown in Figure 6, with the beam direction parallel to the z axis, and are listed below:

- **The azimuthal angle φ :** the angle between the transverse momentum in the xy plane and the x -axis.
- **The pseudorapidity η :** calculated as $\eta = -\log[\tan(\frac{\theta}{2})]$, with θ the polar angle between the z axis and the muon momentum.
- **The transverse momentum p_T :** the component of the muon momentum in the xy frame.

Figure 6: LHC structure and kinematics of a product particle.

The L1 muon φ and η (extrapolated to the vertex), p_T and charge values, given by the μ GMT, are used as inputs of the neural network. φ values have been processed in order to wrap the angle in the $(0, 2\pi)$ range. Fixed precision numbers are used as floating point numbers are not desirable for FPGA implementations. These values are also divided by 256 to get smaller values, an operation that can be easily implemented on hardware through a bit shift.

The muons in the training dataset are taken from the so-called ZeroBias dataset available in the CMS Data Aggregation System. This is a dataset acquired by random triggering on colliding bunches, and not an algorithm-based trigger, avoiding any possible bias. The L1 muons in the ZeroBias dataset have been matched to an offline reconstructed muon using also the tracking system information. Due to the higher resolution available in the offline reconstruction case, the latter is considered as the ground truth for the network predictions.

The distributions of the main kinematic parameters given in input to the network are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: φ , η and p_T distributions of the training dataset.

2.2 Tools

Two main tools have been used for the design and training of the neural network for the FPGA: `hls4ml` and `QKeras`. While `QKeras` can be used to build and train different NN models, `hls4ml` is used to turn them into High-Level Synthesis (HLS) code.

hls4ml `hls4ml` [15] is an open source Python package that is used to design firmware implementations of ML algorithms for FPGAs using the HLS language. It is compatible with common machine learning libraries such as Keras/TensorFlow/QKeras, PyTorch and Onnx. Different neural network architectures such as Fully Connected, 1D and 2D Convolutional, Recurrent Neural Networks and Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTMs), are supported by the tool. It also allows one to adapt the HLS output to user requirements. Some key configurations used for this project are:

- **Fixed Point precision:** it relies on the `ap_fixed<X,Y>` type and it allows to change the fixed point precision format of inputs, outputs, weights, layer outputs and activation functions. Thus, it allows to control the resource usage of the HLS module.
- **Target clock period:** it is the approximate period of the clock with which the neural network will work.
- **DSP reuse factor:** it determines how many times a single multiplier will be used. A value greater than one will lead to a reduction in parallelism, however, it can allow one to significantly reduce the DSP usage on the FPGA.

QKeras This package is an extension of the Keras API, providing quantization-aware neural network models and training [16]. While generating the HLS model of a NN, it allows one to decrease the weight precision, and compress the model, without major accuracy loss.

2.3 Neural Network structure for L1 muons recalibration

To recalibrate the L1 physics objects, generally, two different approaches are used. The first approach is to directly predict the recalibrated values (Figure 8a), while the second is to predict correction terms that will be applied to the L1 quantities (Figure 8b). In this project, both have been examined but since the second one gives in general significantly better results compared to the first one, it is explained in more detail in the following Subsections.

A fully connected neural network with 3 layers, ReLu activation functions and L2 regularization has been instantiated between the Zero Suppression and FIFO Filler modules in the Scouting firmware. To facilitate the development process, the trigger input is emulated directly inside the FPGA using test patterns stored in buffers and containing muons from Run 2 data packed using the Run 3 data format given in Figure 9. The data from every bunch crossing in a LHC orbit is encoded in 6 subsequent 256 bits frames and it contains information about kinematic quantities of L1 muons at the 2nd muon station and extrapolated at the vertex, as well as the orbit number and BX number in an orbit.

Figure 8: Different approaches for μ GMT muons recalibration.

The VCU128 board receives 8 links from μ GMT processor board. For a single bunch crossing, a maximum of 8 candidate muons is supplied by the first 4 input links. The other half supplies an intermediate version of the candidate muons in the trigger processing chain. The 8 possible muons are fed to the NN and the output correction quantities are written to the empty fields of intermediate muon streams, since for the latter the fields with the vertex extrapolated quantities are left empty.

Run-3

Orbit counter											
I		$\eta_{z,raw}$			$\eta_{l,raw}$			Bunch counter			
M		$\eta_{extrap.}$		qual	p_T		$\varphi_{extrap.}$				
	IP	R	$p_{T,unconstr.}$		φ_{raw}			IDX	VC	CH	Iso
			$\eta_{extrap.}$		qual	p_T		$\varphi_{extrap.}$			
	IP	R	$p_{T,unconstr.}$		φ_{raw}			IDX	VC	CH	Iso

Figure 9: Run 3 data format of μ GMT [14]. Legend: IM=Intermediate Marker, qual=quality, IP=Impact Parameter, R=Reserved, IDX=Muson Index, VC=Valid Charge, CH=Charge, Iso=Isolation.

2.4 Neural Network model selection

For the NN performance optimization, several configurations such as different libraries (Keras, QKeras), precisions (`ap_fixed<12,3>`, `ap_fixed<18,6>`), regularization constants and number of hidden neurons, are investigated. Additionally, on some models a pruning with different ratios (p) is applied, based on the weight magnitudes. This optimization allows to reduce the required FPGA resources by pruning weights that are less relevant for the NN prediction, namely small weights in their absolute value. To evaluate the performance of the considered models, various metrics have been used, starting from the value of the loss function after training. Based on these metrics, 6 models are chosen to be further examined. All these models have 3 layers, ReLU activation functions and L2 regularization with 10^{-4} regularization constant, and they are listed below along with their distinctive characteristics:

- Model 1: Keras – 64 hidden neuron - `ap_fixed<18,6>` precision.
- Model 2: Keras – 16 hidden neuron - `ap_fixed<12,3>` precision.
- Model 3: QKeras – 64 hidden neuron - `ap_fixed<18,6>` precision - 0.2 pruning.
- Model 4: QKeras – 32 hidden neuron - `ap_fixed<18,6>` precision - 0.5 pruning.

- Model 5: QKeras – 32 hidden neuron - ap_fixed<12,3> precision - 0.2 pruning.
- Model 6: QKeras – 64 hidden neuron - ap_fixed<12,3> precision - 0.5 pruning.

Loss Values To get a first insight on the performance of the selected models, the logarithmic hyperbolic cosine loss of all of them has been taken into account for a comparison. The values are reported in Table 1 and the best results for each category are highlighted. In general, a smaller loss translates to a more accurate model.

Loss Values of All Models												
Size	Reg.	Keras Model	Em. HLS (18,6)	Em. HLS (12,3)	Qkeras (18,6) p=0.2	Qkeras (18,6) p=0.5	Qkeras (12,3) p=0.2	Qkeras (12,3) p=0.5	Em. QHLS (18,6) p=0.2	Em. QHLS (18,6) p=0.5	Em. QHLS (12,3) p=0.2	Em. QHLS (12,3) p=0.5
64	10^{-4}	0.1079	0.1281	0.2008	0.1074	0.1076	0.1081	0.1075	0.1266	0.1262	0.1725	0.1662
64	10^{-3}	0.1089	0.1348	0.2855	0.1119	0.1125	0.1121	0.1113	0.1312	0.1307	0.2092	0.1851
32	10^{-4}	0.1087	0.1284	0.203	0.1083	0.108	0.1086	0.1083	0.1277	0.1257	0.1691	0.1717
32	10^{-3}	0.1095	0.1296	0.2134	0.1132	0.1122	0.1122	0.1123	0.1331	0.1311	0.1803	0.181
16	10^{-4}	0.1109	0.1308	0.1715	0.1094	0.1112	0.1121	0.1114	0.1285	0.1293	0.1733	0.172
16	10^{-3}	0.1114	0.131	0.5132	0.113	0.1136	0.1132	0.1124	0.1316	0.134	0.1766	0.1755

Table 1: Logarithmic hyperbolic cosine loss values of different models.

Offline reconstructed quantities vs L1 NN-corrected quantities The performance of the 6 selected models is further assessed by comparing the L1 quantities corrected with the NN prediction, with the offline reconstructed quantities. The resolution peaks for each quantity are plotted and fitted with a Gaussian distribution, from which the Full Width Half Maximum (FWHM) can be extracted and used as a metric. An example of the resolution peak plots is shown Figure 10, where the results are obtained using the Model 1 (64 neurons per layer and ap_fixed<18,6> precision).

Additionally, the percentage of data point inside the core (data points falling inside the 0.16 and 0.84 quantiles of the fitted and unit-normalized Gaussian) is calculated for the performance evaluation. For all the models, mean, standard deviation, FWHM and percentage of data inside the core are reported in Table 2. The best results (smallest for mean, standard deviation and FWHM, greatest for percentage) have been highlighted.

Figure 10: The plots of the resolution peaks for each kinematic quantity, obtained from the differences between the offline reconstructed values and the NN-corrected L1 quantities (blue, $X_{L1,vtx} - X_{reco} + \Delta X_{pred}$) or the original L1 quantities (orange, $X_{L1,vtx} - X_{reco}$). The given results are obtained using Model 1.

Model	φ				η				p_T			
	Mean	Sigma	FWHM	Data in core (%)	Mean	Sigma	FWHM	Data in core (%)	Mean	Sigma	FWHM	Data in core (%)
M 1	0.0002	0.092	0.217	58.36	-0.004	0.039	0.092	66.54	0.0229	0.157	0.369	70.16
M 2	0.0136	0.087	0.205	64.94	0.0122	0.043	0.101	69.1	0.0416	0.165	0.388	69.92
M 3	0.0071	0.089	0.209	58.42	0.0038	0.039	0.092	64.28	0.0147	0.153	0.360	70.44
M 4	0.0092	0.092	0.217	63.45	0.0003	0.041	0.096	64.42	0.0165	0.155	0.365	67.67
M 5	0.0182	0.087	0.205	60.80	0.0107	0.041	0.096	64.59	0.0436	0.159	0.374	69.14
M 6	0.0132	0.090	0.212	59.82	0.0177	0.040	0.094	65.94	0.0334	0.156	0.367	67.55

Table 2: Mean, standard deviation, FWHM and data in core percentage of models. The best model is highlighted in red.

Hardware resource usage Since the networks are implemented on an FPGA, the limited available resources of the chip is a significant factor to take into account for the optimal model choice. Thus, as last step of the selection process, these 6 models have been synthesized using `hls4ml` to observe how different configurations affect the resource usage and which models are suitable for the hardware implementation. The VCU128 FPGA board has around 9 thousand DSP, 2.6 million Flip-Flops (FF) and 1.3 million Look-Up-Tables (LUTs). DSP, FF and LUT usages in terms of percentages with respect to the VCU128 FPGA board are provided in Table 3. Additionally, the latency of the models in terms of clock cycles is presented.

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
Latency	16	10	16	15	15	15
DSP (%)	39.24	5.04	23.24	10.85	6.59	11.06
FF (%)	3.36	0.26	1.85	0.93	0.53	0.95
LUT (%)	15.52	1.52	5.98	2.60	3.27	6.05

Table 3: Latency in terms of AXI clock cycles and DSP, FF and LUT usage percentages for the 6 chosen models.

The results show that as number of hidden neurons and precision increases, the resource usage also increases. Moreover, given the performance of the model, NN architectures obtained from QKeras have a lower resource usage with respect to standard Keras models quantized in `hls4ml`. In addition, pruning and increasing the DSP reuse factor results in a further reduction of the needed resources for the implementation.

3 FPGA Implementation and Deployment

The second and main part of the project is the integration of the NN into the firmware. As mentioned before, Virtex UltraScale+ HBM VCU128 FPGA Evaluation Kit (Figure 11) has been used for the application.

For test and development purposes, L1 μ GMT muon patterns are generated on the hardware with the Run 3 data format. In one bunch crossing, there can be up to 8 muons and all those muons should be fed into a NN before the next bunch crossing data arrives (within 6 AXI clock cycles). Firstly, required data (φ , η , p_T and charge) must be extracted from the bunch crossing data block frame. Then, they are processed so that they can be fed into the NN.

After implementing the pre-processing part, three different approaches based on the number of NNs (8, 4 and 2) on the firmware have been tested. As the number of neural networks instances increases, the resource usage increases as well, which can lead to timing violations and a longer routing time.

(a) VCU128 FPGA board

(b) VCU128 hardware setup

Figure 11: Virtex UltraScale+ HBM VCU128 FPGA Evaluation Kit.

Additionally, as Table 3 indicates, bigger models can take up to 40% of the available DSP on the VU37P chip. So, it is not possible to deploy too many instances of neural networks on the board. Therefore, one of the aims is to reduce the number of NN instances to the minimum.

Vivado simulations have been employed to speed up the workflow of design implementation and validation of the VHDL design of the NN module. The simulation of the design has been also exploited to tune buffer sizes and VHDL delta delays. For the output validation in simulation, the NN predictions are dumped and analyzed for a comparison with the software results, considered as reference.

After having assessed the correctness of the design on simulation, the firmware has been synthesized, implemented and deployed on hardware in a test setup for the final validation step.

3.1 Resource Usage Optimization

Resource utilizations and timings of all three approaches have been compared. Neural network models use LUTs, DSPs and FFs and the main limiting factor is the availability of DSPs. Different configurations such as DSP reuse factor or target clock frequency have also been tested in this step.

(a) 8 NN approach

(b) 4 NN approach

(c) 2 NN approach

Figure 12: Different approaches to optimize resource usage.

8 Neural Networks The first approach is having 8 neural networks, one for each candidate muon (Figure 12a). It is the easiest and most direct method since there is no need to buffer input data. For test purposes, a Keras neural network with 32 neurons per layer and `ap_fixed<18,6>` precision has been used. To fit the model, DSP reuse factor is increased to 4 and the target clock period is set

to 4 ns. The time needed to synthesize and implement this design is around 13 hours, resulting in significant timing violations. The details on the resource usage and on the severeness of the timing slacks are reported in Figure 13. This result proves that the approach is not feasible with the target hardware of the project.

Figure 13: Resource utilization with 8 NN approach.

4 Neural Networks The second approach has been to instantiate 4 NNs, feeding each of them with the two possible candidate muons per each link (Figure 12b). In addition to the first approach, it required to tune the buffer depths to store input data for long enough time. For test purposes, a much smaller model than the first one, a QKeras NN with 32 neurons per layer and `ap_fixed<18,6>` precision (Model 4 in previous Section) have been used. DSP reuse factor is reduced to 2 and the target clock period of the application is set to 2 ns to make the design more robust to timing violations at the price of a slightly higher resource usage. The time needed for the implementation is reduced to approximately 1.33 hours and the details of the implemented design are reported in Figure 14. This approach improves the routing of the design and is not affected by timing violations.

Figure 14: Resource utilization with 4 NN approach.

2 Neural Networks For further optimization, the number of NN instances has been reduced to 2 with 4 candidate muons for each, which is also the minimum allowed by the firmware specifics and by the application (Figure 12c). For test purposes, a QKeras NN with 32 neurons per layer and `ap_fixed<18,6>` precision (Model 4 in previous Section) have been used. Since increasing the DSP reuse factor increases the time interval between 2 inputs, it is not possible to use it in this approach. The target clock is set to 3 ns in order to reduce the latency and to avoid timing violations. The synthesis and implementation take 1.1 hours in this case and resource usage in percentage is given in

Figure 15. This solution does not give timing violations, and it is the most optimal presented in this work.

Figure 15: Resource utilization with 2 NN approach.

In all three approaches, simulation predictions reproduce accurately the software ones. The predictions of the neural networks are stored in the empty fields of the intermediate muons streams, namely in the raw φ and η . This solution requires to truncate the 18-bits output of the NN for each parameter to fit in the empty fields, resulting in a small loss of precision. Small discrepancies between software and hardware results at this stage are due to the previous reason.

After synthesizing, the implemented firmware has been tested in the test setup located in the DAQ test laboratory of CERN Building 40 (Figure 11b). The output stream with the zero-suppressed data and the NN predictions is sent to a Dell PowerEdge R320 server using Direct Memory Access through the PCIe slots of the PCI bridge on the chassis in the test setup. All NN results in the output stream reproduce accurately the results from software and from the Vivado simulation, confirming the successful integration of the NN in the Level-1 Scouting firmware for the Xilinx VCU128 board.

4 Conclusion

The purpose of this work is to integrate a NN to the CMS Level-1 Scouting firmware for online recalibration of μ GMT muons using the Xilinx VCU128 FPGA board. The goals are achieved in 2 steps.

The first step is to generate a NN to predict the correction terms to the L1 quantities for the recalibration. Neural networks with different configurations such as library (Keras/QKeras), regularization constant, pruning ratio and number of hidden neurons are tested to get an ideal model. Later, they are converted to HLS packages using the `hls4ml` tool, which also returns the resource usage estimations. The results show that while bigger models (64 neurons) perform slightly better. Since they have a greater resource usage, it might not be possible to use them in the hardware implementation. Therefore, alternative models developed with the QKeras library and with a smaller number of weights, can be used without major accuracy loss.

The second step and main part of the project is integrating the NN to the firmware. After generating the L1 μ GMT test muons on hardware in Run 3 format, the parameters of interest are extracted and pre-processed. Three different approaches based on the number of NN have been investigated and it has been observed that, using less NNs is preferred due to hardware limitations. Therefore, the 2 NN approach is chosen as the most efficient method. The final firmware is tested with the test setup and results exactly match with software predictions indicating that the integration has been completed successfully.

5 References

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